

Teaching with Technology: A Study on Faculty Attitude towards IT Adoption in Classroom Teaching

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K. Shobitha Kumari

*M.Com, Assistant Professor
Jain College CGS, V.V.Puram, Bangalore*

Shawar Saleem

*M.Com, NET, Assistant Professor
Jain College CGS, V V Puram, Bangalore*

Abstract

We have witnessed tremendous growth in Information technology during last 2 decades. This has posed many challenges to both faculty and institutions. Why is the integration of technology so appealing to some faculty and not to others? Our study focuses on perception of faculty towards integration of Information technology in classroom teaching. The level of integration of information technology by faculties in class room teaching may be influenced by many factors. Study is also concerned with those factors which has greater influence. All the respondents who took part in survey were screened to make sure that they have basic knowledge on information and communication technology. The findings of the study indicates that faculties are not against the adoption of IT in teaching instead they feel that traditional teaching methods and IT should be blended properly which can create wonders.

Keywords: Technology, Software, Technology Integration.

Introduction

When talking about education, people often confuse it with schooling. Education is an important medium of acquiring essential knowledge and skills. Technology has impacted almost every aspect of life today. And education is no exception. The use of information and communication technologies in education can play a crucial role in providing new and innovative forms of support to faculties, students. Today massive amounts of information’s are available at ones fingertips through the internet.

Technology also has begun to change the roles of teachers. In traditional classroom, teacherIs the primary source of information, and learners passively receive it. However because of access to information and educational opportunities that technology has enabled, in many classroom today we see the teacher’s role shifting to guide on the side. Therefor Faculties are expected to achieve technological competence and implement better forms of teaching

practice which improves students learning experience. However we have found out that at many schools and collages class room teaching is still dominated by traditional education characterized by textbooks, blackboards because most of the faculties do not use information technologies in classroom teaching. Teachers need to use technology strategically and use it as a tool to student learning. Integration of technology promotes problem solving and critical thinking skills among students.

Statement of Problem

Even though it is said that technology has become increasingly important in every educational level, it is not accepted by all the faculties due to certain factors. So we try to capture the perception of faculty members on integration of IT in classroom teaching.

Review of Literature

Charles buabengandoh (2012) conducted a study on “factors influencing teachers adoption and integration of information and communication technology into teaching”, his paper reviews personal, institutional and technological factors that encourage teachers use of computer technology in teaching and learning processes.

Ruggiero D., & Mong has done research on “The teacher technology integration experience :practice and reflection in the classroom Has given certain recommendations for restructuring professional development on strategies for contextualization technology integration in the classroom.”

Alabama Journal of Educational Leadership (2018) has published a journal on “Factors affecting technology integration in the classroom”, which discusses factors such as poor infrastructure, inadequate technology, lack of sufficient technology tools, and teacher perception that affect technology integration .

Bidhan Roy (2019),asst professor, Manbhum Institute of Education & Social Science, Nadia, Purulia, West Bengal,conducted a study on “Role of ICT in enhancing classroom teaching-learning process in India”,whichhighlights

Scot Reid (2002) has done research on “The integration information and communication technology into classroom teaching”. This study provides new images of teachers who are pioneers in the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the classes they teach.

Objective

1. To understand impact of IT on classroom teaching
2. To understand perception of faculties on usage of IT in classroom delivery
3. To find out the difference in understanding level with and without usage of IT
4. To find out barriers for the successful implementation of IT if any.

Scope of the Study

This study helps in understanding the perception of faculties towards integration of ICT in class room teaching.

Limitations of the Study

1. Research is confined only to a limited sample size of 30
2. Research is confined only on attitude of faculties without considering students attitude.

Research Methodology

The authors would like to specifically focus on attitude of faculties and to what extend technology has taken place in day to day life.

Descriptive Research Design

Descriptive research is a type of research design is description of state of affairs as it is at present. A close ended online questionnaire was administered to the respondents.

Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling technique was employed in selection of sample.

Sample Size

The sample size of this study constitutes the faculties with total sample size of 30

Data Collection Method

A questionnaire was used to collect primary data since primary data is one original in nature.

Data Analysis and Interpretation**Table 1 Demographic Details of the Respondents**

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	10	33
Female	20	67
Total	30	100
Work Experience		
< 1 Year	3	10
1 to 5 Years	19	63
> 5 Years	8	27
Total	30	100
Educational Qualification		
Ph.D.	6	20
Master Degree	24	80
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred out that out of the total respondent's 33 % were male and 67% were female. 10 % of respondents were new to the profession where as 63% have 1 to 5 years of work experience and 27% having more than 5 years' work experience. 20% of respondents are Ph.D. holders and 80% of the respondents with master's degree.

Table 2 Nature of Subjects Handle

Subjects	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Theory	5	17
Practical	9	30
Both	16	53
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that 17% of respondents handle only theory subjects 30% practical subjects where as 53% of respondents handle both practical's and theory.

Table 3 Level of Competence

Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
MS Word		
Excellent	23	77
Good	6	20
Fair	1	3
None	0	0
Total	30	100
E-Mail		
Excellent	26	87
Good	3	10
Fair	1	3
None	0	0
Total	30	100
Internet Browsing		
Excellent	28	93
Good	2	7
Fair	0	0
None	0	0
Total	30	100
PPT		
Excellent	27	90
Good	3	10
Fair	0	0
None	0	0
Total	30	100
Others		
Excellent	17	57
Good	4	13
Fair	4	13
None	5	17
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that self-assessed level of competence of faculties is very good. Around 77% have excellent knowledge of MS Word, 87 % in mailing and 93% respondents have good knowledge on web browsing and 90% are very good in PPT an 57% in others.

Table 4 How often you Integrate Computer Technologies in your Teaching activities

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Frequently	11	37
Always	10	33
Rarely	9	30
Not at all	0	0
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that 37% of faculties frequently use IT in classroom teaching, 33% of respondents always integrate IT in classroom teaching, 30% rarely use IT in classroom teaching.

Table 5 Most often used Software Programme in Classroom Teaching

Technology	No. of Respondents	Percentage
MS Word	4	13
PPT	20	67
Spreadsheet	0	0
Others	6	20
None	0	0
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that 67% of the respondents use PPT in classroom teaching, and 13% of them use MS Word, and 20% of the respondents use other IT related software in class

Table 6 Barriers on Increased Use of IT

Acceptance	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Time to learn new technologies		
Strongly Agree	7	23
Agree	8	27
Disagree	12	40
Strongly Disagree	2	7
Neutral	1	3
Total	30	100
Classroom infrastructure		
Strongly Agree	10	34
Agree	7	23
Disagree	9	30
Strongly Disagree	3	10
Neutral	1	3
Total	30	100

Knowledge about applying IT in my teaching		
Strongly Agree	4	13
Agree	12	40
Disagree	7	24
Strongly Disagree	6	20
Neutral	1	3
Total	30	100
Nature of subjects		
Strongly Agree	23	77
Agree	5	17
Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	1	3
Neutral	1	3
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that 77% of the respondents strongly agree that nature of the subject they handle is the biggest barrier for increased use of IT. 40% of the respondents disagree that time to learn a new technology is a barrier. 34% of them strongly agree that class room infrastructure is an adding factor for increased use of IT in classroom teaching. 40% of the respondents agree that knowledge on usage of proper technology is also on of the barrier here.

Table 7 Positive Impact of IT in Classroom Teaching

Acceptance	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Increases students concentration		
Strongly Agree	6	20
Agree	9	30
Disagree	14	47
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Neutral	1	3
Total	30	100
Students understand more easily		
Strongly Agree	7	23
Agree	15	50
Disagree	8	27
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Neutral	0	0
Total	30	100
Classroom management becomes easier		
Strongly Agree	13	44
Agree	3	10
Disagree	7	23

Strongly Disagree	7	23
Neutral	0	0
Total	30	100
Students remember more easily		
Strongly Agree	8	27
Agree	10	33
Disagree	8	27
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Neutral	4	13
Total	30	100

From the above table it is inferred that 47% of the respondents disagree with the fact that usage of IT will increase the student’s concentration. At the same time 50% of the faculties agree that students understand more easily if IT is used .44% of faculties feel that with the usage of IT in classroom, classroom management becomes easier, and 33 % of the respondents agree that students remember things easily with the integration of IT in classroom teaching

Findings

- Researchers found out that out of the respondent’s majority were female respondents and majority of them have more than 1 year teaching experience. Only few respondents are PhD holders.
- The majority of respondents handle both practical and theory subjects.
- Researcher also found out that majority of respondents has proficiency in one or other forms of IT. Majority of them have good knowledge of MS word, ppt and internet browsing.
- Most of them frequently integrate IT in classroom teaching. Statistics also shows that there is no faculties who have not used IT at all in classroom teaching.
- It is also found out that majority of them use PPT to make classroom teaching more effective.
- There are many barriers on increased use of IT in classroom teaching. The one of the main reason is the nature of the subject they handle. Adding to that majority of them feel that classroom infrastructure is also main reason which restricts on from increased use of IT. and few feels that unless you have proper knowledge on how to adopt IT in your subjects, it will not make any sense.
- Majority of the respondents agree that use of IT in classroom teaching will increase the understanding level of the students and also it makes classroom management easier.

Suggestions

It is evident from the study that technology in education is the biggest change in teaching we will ever see. There is a saying “if you want to be on the cutting edge, don’t sit down”, if you have gone 3 or 4 years using the same technology you are comfortable with, make yourself uncomfortable and use something new. Your ability to adopt new technology will influence positively on your students too. It is better to mix teaching styles often and students would have a better learning experience. Video sessions are good option to grab student’s attention and focus. At the same time proper knowledge on the technologies you use is major factor that decides the effectiveness of IT.

A recommendation is that technology should be used to enhance education by engaging students into higher order thinking skills and not as a substitute for teaching.

Conclusion

Today’s economy is based on global perspective. we need to compete and collaborate with the world the education must be catered along these lines. In order to get job in today’s workplace higher order thinking skills are required. And this is possible with the use of technology. Technology is versatile and valuable tool teaching and learning and becoming a way of life. The most important thing is that teachers need to be prepared to use these technologies effectively

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